

Assessing France's Third Way: French Bilateral Policy with Indo-Pacific Middle Powers

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France, despite being a European power, possesses considerable territories in the Indo-Pacific and in recent years has aimed to expand its role in the region, particularly through bilateral relations with middle powers such as India and Australia. The overall success of this approach has remained largely unassessed in academic literature, and this paper helps to close this gap by applying a Realist analysis to France's bilateral policies. It finds that France has achieved certain successes in expanding its relations with states such as India and Japan through military exercises, trade, and strategic partnerships. In doing so, France has effectively reinforced its regional legitimacy. France has also faced challenges, most prominently the scuppering of its submarine deal with Australia and its struggles to achieve strategic alignment with Indo-Pacific partners. This paper argues that France has thus failed to accomplish its aim of a 'third way' in the Indo-Pacific.

INTRODUCTION

At a G20 summit held in September 2021, French President Emmanuel Macron made an “extraordinary accusation” when he was asked if he thought that Australian Prime Minister Scott Morrison was a liar. Macron replied, “I don't think, I know” (Probyn, 2021). The reason for this caustic remark, and the accompanying expulsion of French ambassadors to Australia and the United States, was the cancellation of a 90 billion AUD submarine deal (Murphy, 2021). But why did France care so much about an agreement with faraway middle power Australia? Why had the French agreed to such a huge arrangement in the first place? The answers lie in France's complex and developing strategy in the Indo-Pacific, an under-analysed, yet important feature of the region's evolving geopolitics.

Although France may seem an unlikely player in the Indo-Pacific, it has substantial overseas territories in the region. France has made a concerted effort to build up its bilateral partnerships in the Indo-Pacific over the last decade, particularly with India, Australia and Japan, amongst other countries. While the strengthening of these relationships has been noted, the subject has been relatively neglected in the literature (Scott, 2019), and there remains a need to assess the collective successes and failures of France's approach in the region. To investigate this, the following research question will be addressed: “Has France successfully used bilateral relationships to achieve its goals in the Indo-Pacific region over the last decade?”

This paper uses a Realist approach to examine France's bilateral relationships in the Indo-Pacific. Realism is an International Relations (IR) theory that describes the international order as fundamentally chaotic, with states competing to protect their own sovereignty and power (Jervis, 1999). Realism is one of the most prominent IR theories, and although it has been criticised for its tendency to neglect the role of domestic politics or international institutions (Glaser, 2003), it remains appropriate for this analysis. Centred around individual states as the primary actors in the international realm, it is well-suited to evaluating the actions of one state, in this case, France. Additionally, Realism's focus on disorderly and competitive international orders makes it apposite for describing the conditions in the Indo-Pacific region, which have become increasingly contested and militarised (O'Keefe, 2020).

The 'Indo-Pacific' label should also be interrogated, as it has emerged relatively recently and not without dispute. The term 'Indo-Pacific' has been promoted by US-aligned states and incorporates the Indian and Pacific oceans into one wide area of strategic interest (Medcalf, 2014, p. 461). Analysts such

as Wesley Morgan have argued that this aims to recast the region in the image of Western democracies, as “In this framing, maritime democracies—particularly the US, Australia, Japan, and India—will increasingly work together to maintain balance in the regional order” (2020, pp. 47-8) because disparate powers like Japan and India are now placed in the same, implicitly anti-China sphere. China itself has resisted using the ‘Indo-Pacific’ framework, characterising the term as part of a wider containment strategy targeting it (Ye, 2020, pp. 206-7). As much as the Indo-Pacific is a loaded term, it remains an appropriate framing given the general shift of geopolitical tension towards the region since the end of the Cold War, due primarily to China’s rise and resulting contestation of the American-led order (Medcalf, 2014). Additionally, France itself has used the term to contextualise its own regional actions since 2018, abandoning previous labels like ‘Asia-Pacific’ (Lechervy, 2019).

This paper will establish France’s exact stake in the region, along with its primary objectives: securing its regional sovereignty and legitimacy as well as implementing a peaceful ‘third way’ in the Indo-Pacific. It will discuss France’s bilateral relations, especially those with India and Australia, before drawing wider conclusions about the successes and failures of France’s strategy. Analysis will reveal that while France has succeeded in shoring up its legitimacy as an Indo-Pacific state, it is yet to chart a peaceful ‘third way’ and struggles to effectively realign potential allies like Australia.

FRANCE’S STAKE IN THE INDO-PACIFIC

France possesses considerable territories in the Indo-Pacific, which form the basis for its actions in the region. French territories in the Indian Ocean include the islands of Réunion and Mayotte, while its possessions in the Pacific include New Caledonia and French Polynesia. Together, all of these Indo-Pacific territories contain more than 1.5 million people, but also give France access to a vast Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) in the oceans, the second largest in the world (Bondaz, 2023). This EEZ grants France exclusive rights to marine resources within its zone, such as fishing and mining; French Polynesia’s EEZ likely contains extensive underwater minerals, including cobalt (Le Meur et al., 2018). 93% of France’s EEZ is in the Indo-Pacific, and control of this vast sea area provides valuable economic and strategic resources (Bondaz, 2023). By virtue of these territories, France is directly influenced by events in the Indo-Pacific, making it a unique player as a distant European state with direct local interest. Thus, for Bouchard and Crumplin, “France is both a regional state, at least on behalf of its islands, and an external great power significantly involved in the region” (Bouchard and Crumplin, 2011, p. 175). French ambitions are not limited by these ‘two faces’ in the Indo-Pacific; instead, it perceives itself as an influential player, as suggested by Macron’s 2018 claim that, “France is a great power (une grande puissance) of the Indo-Pacific” (Macron, 2018). While France has backed this up through its maintenance of some 7000 troops across regional French territories (Ministère des Armées, 2019), it is nonetheless significantly weaker than resident states.

These possessions form the basis of France’s objectives in the Indo-Pacific. In its 2021 Indo-Pacific Strategy, France declared four ‘pillars’ of its strategy, foremost of which was security and defence: “Ensuring and defending the integrity and sovereignty of France, the protection of its citizens, its territories, and its EEZ” (Ministry for Europe and for Foreign Affairs, 2021, pp. 6-7). These declarations were made alongside commitments to economic objectives, upholding the multilateral rule of law, and climate action. From a Realist perspective, the protection of sovereignty and security is a key goal for any state (Tang, 2009, p. 588), and France is no exception, however distant its territories may be. Connected to its goal of maintaining regional sovereignty are crucial concerns about France’s legitimacy as an Indo-Pacific state. France’s colonial history poses problems, as scholars such as David Scott note: “France seeks regional legitimacy so as to change the perceptions by others of France as an illegitimate and outdated European colonial power” (Scott, 2019, p. 79). This is by no means a theoretical issue for France, as demonstrated by recent internal disputes over the status and future of New Caledonia (Al Jazeera, 2024); France seeks regional validation for its continued presence in the Indo-Pacific. Achieving legitimacy can help France protect its national security, because if France is seen to be a legitimate regional actor, its continued control over possessions like New Caledonia and their resources will not be opposed. If French possessions were to become independent, this would constitute a major failure of French foreign policy.

One major threat to French interests in the region is China. While France maintains significant trading links with China, their relationship has become increasingly difficult since Xi Jinping came to power in 2013. France is troubled by China’s growing influence and the nature of its actions. A recent 600-page report by French military think tank IRSEM labelled China’s actions in the Indo-Pacific and

elsewhere “a Machiavellian moment” (Charon and Jeangène Vilmer, 2021, p. 15). Furthermore, China has flouted various norms of the rules-based order in the Indo-Pacific, through its aggression towards Taiwan, internal suppression of opposition, trade disputes, and its violation of maritime law and militarisation in the South China Sea (Leplâtre, 2023). As France’s influence in the region is reliant on its maritime power, it is particularly threatened by China’s disregard for the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea (Gilli, 2019, p. 19). France has vocally condemned China’s actions in numerous statements and has backed resolutions such as the 2016 UN Arbitration Ruling that labelled China’s ‘nine-dash line’, which claims control of a large part of the South China Sea, as unlawful (Embassy of France in Manila, 2024). France has even gone as far as engaging in naval exercises in the disputed region (The Economic Times, 2024), demonstrating its opposition to China. France’s bilateral actions with resident Indo-Pacific states have also intensified from the mid-2010s, with new trade and defence deals such as the Enhanced Strategic Partnership with Australia from 2017 and the Joint Strategic Vision of India-France Cooperation from 2018; arguably, this intensification has flowed in direct response to China’s rise (Gilli, 2019, p. 20).

More broadly, China poses problems for other aspects of French foreign policy through its close collaboration with Russia, as well as its opposition to NATO and other Western blocs with which France is aligned. Scholar Mahima Duggal illustrates China’s role in defining France’s regional actions: “France’s pivot toward the Indo-Pacific, and its endeavour to influence and shape the norms in the region, and contribute to building an inclusive, rules-based regional order, are drawn staunchly on China’s growing presence” (Duggal, 2022, p. 5). Indeed, there is a clear temporal link to France’s recent pivot towards the region, as it only began using the Indo-Pacific framework in the mid-2010s, releasing numerous foreign policy documents since 2018 pertinent to the Indo-Pacific (Scott, 2019). This has occurred in the same timeframe as escalating Chinese aggression in the region.

To fully understand France’s objectives in the Indo-Pacific, it is necessary to examine its relationship with the other regional superpower, the US. The US has taken an aggressive stance towards China, criticising its foreign policy and engaging in a trade war. In contrast, French commentators argue that, “France’s Indo-Pacific strategy departs substantially from the US strategy, which tends to be both confrontational and over-militarised” (Nicolas, 2019). Indeed, while France does oppose China, it also fears the effects of the US’s confrontational approach, which presents the greatest risk of conflict (Duggal, 2022, p. 12). Researchers such as Éric Mottet have identified that France’s opposition to China’s growing influence and action does not constitute an alignment with the US, but instead encourages France to pursue a “third way (troisième voie)” (Mottet et al., 2023, p. 342). This third way aligns with neither superpower but instead pursues an autonomous foreign policy where France can reinforce regional peace through the role of facilitator (Mottet et al., 2023, p. 342). The growing divide between the US and China would potentially force France to choose between the two superpowers, constraining its agency and potentially jeopardising its security. Instead, pursuing a non-committal balancing act, similar to that pursued by many Southeast Asian states, offers a more appealing role for France, where it can limit potential risks (Mahbubani, 2023, p. 131). This is an ambitious goal for France to have in the Indo-Pacific given its limited presence in the region, but it has nonetheless defined part of its actions over the last decade.

France has other secondary objectives in the Indo-Pacific. For scholars such as Andrea Gilli, maintaining the rules-based order despite growing Chinese power is merely one of several French aims in the region, where “nuclear non-proliferation... and dealing with non-state actors and non-security threats” are just as significant (Gilli, 2019, p. 18). While French interest in these issues cannot be denied – as a nuclear power, France has an interest in non-proliferation regarding North Korea, and it has taken substantial actions in terms of climate and anti-terrorism globally (Gilli, 2019, p. 19) – this is an incorrect assessment of France’s main aims. In recent years, France’s actions have clearly become focused on containing regional hegemons, as evidenced by the expansion of its bilateral relations with Indo-Pacific middle powers. Finally, there is the aim of wider EU involvement in the Indo-Pacific, an issue that French academics have identified as a central French goal, but one that has been received more sceptically in English-language discussions. Mottet and others contend that the “French approach largely relies on European commitment in the region” (Mottet et al., 2023, p. 342), which may be an ambitious hope. While France has clear reasons for involvement in the Indo-Pacific, no other European nation has territories in the region aside from the non-EU United Kingdom. While France occupies a central position in the EU, and European states do have other reasons for involvement in the Indo-Pacific, EU positions towards China remain contested, as Angela Stanzel

notes: “EU member states remain vulnerable to Beijing’s ‘divide and rule’ approach” (Stanzel, 2017, p. 38). The differing attitudes and aims of EU states mean that they are unlikely to operate as a bloc towards China (Stanzel, 2017, p. 38). While these minor objectives of France should be considered, it is clear that France’s aims in the Indo-Pacific are centred around two main goals: maintaining sovereignty and regional legitimacy, and France’s ambitious hopes of encouraging a third way in the Indo-Pacific.

REGIONAL BILATERAL ACTIONS

France’s foreign policy in the Indo-Pacific is defined markedly by its bilateral relationships. While other actors in the region, such as the US, Australia and Japan, have successfully developed extensive mini- and multilateral arrangements, France has struggled to do so, remaining restricted to bilateral relations as the base of its Indo-Pacific policy. Multilateral forums have been a key feature of the Indo-Pacific for decades, including economic and political partnerships such as Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC), the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), the Pacific Islands Forum (PIF), and the unsuccessful Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP) (Wirth and Jenne, 2022). Despite its undeniable presence in the region and influential position within global multilateral arrangements, such as its seat on the UN Security Council and membership of the G20, France has found itself excluded from these regional multilateral organisations. Although France is not a member of APEC, ASEAN, the PIF or the prospective TPP, and has been limited to a marginal presence in these organisations, it does participate in ASEAN’s ‘regional forum’ through the EU, remains a member of the Pacific Community, and is a ‘dialogue partner’ with the PIF. In 2016, French Polynesia and New Caledonia, two French overseas territories, were accepted into the PIF (MacLellan, 2016). This was a successful outcome of France’s attempts to legitimise its possessions in the Indo-Pacific, particularly because this was a decision supported by the French authorities, rather than independence-minded New Caledonians (MacLellan, 2016). Nonetheless, neither of these territories is directly controlled by France, as they are governed largely by self-elected congresses, and France remains partially excluded from direct participation in regional forums.

In recent years, states have also attempted to build smaller multistate partnerships, most prominently the Quad (the US, Japan, India, and Australia) and AUKUS (Australia, the UK and the US), which have been labelled ‘minilateral’ (Koga, 2022, p. 27). Minilateral actions have also been pursued by China, such as through the China-Korea-Japan Trilateral Summits. Nonetheless, as scholar Kei Koga asserts, “During the 2010s, a new minilateral momentum emerged in response to China’s growing assertiveness” (Koga, 2022, p. 30). These new minilateral China-opposed coalitions that have developed over the last decade do not necessarily align with France’s aims. While France has had some minor minilateral participation with India and Australia in the form of ministerial dialogues, where the three countries “shared mutual concerns regarding the strategic, security, economic and environmental challenges in the Indo-Pacific region” (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2021), the limits to France’s minilateral achievements are also clear. France’s 2021 Indo-Pacific Strategy notes in particular the opportunity to use regional bilateral partnerships for deeper “co-operation in multilateral organisations, for example... the G20” (Ministère de l’Europe et des Affaires étrangères, 2021, p. 40).

As France lacks access to the key multilateral organisations and partnerships that are available to other middle powers and Indo-Pacific minnows, it is forced to tread a different line from other Western-aligned states such as Japan and Australia. The reasons for France’s disadvantaged position in Indo-Pacific forums likely lie in its lack of legitimacy as an actor in the region: if France were perceived as a more legitimate member of the Indo-Pacific community, membership of these groups may be more readily available. The PIF was even formed specifically to exclude French involvement, as France’s dominant position in the South Pacific Commission (today the Pacific Community) had prevented smaller Pacific states from criticising French nuclear policy (MacLellan, 2016). Nonetheless, France still aims to assert itself within the Indo-Pacific, and, without access to major multilateral and minilateral partnerships, French foreign policy in the region has instead shaped itself around bilateral partnerships with regional powers, notably India and Australia. Indeed, while France’s relationships with the US and China form an important part of its regional strategy, as has already been discussed, France has primarily tried to assert itself through bilateral partnerships with regional states, which is the focus of this analysis. So, how have France’s relationships with Indo-Pacific middle powers progressed? Has France been able to use them to achieve its goals in the region?

INDIA

Perhaps the most important pillar of France's bilateral actions in the Indo-Pacific is its long-standing and growing cooperation with India. Since 1998, the two countries have worked together closely through their Strategic Partnership, which has formed the basis of their relationship (Sharma, 2022, p. 236). The two states have long cooperated on issues such as defence, civil nuclear development and space programmes, and in recent years this cooperation has been expanded and enhanced, especially in the form of naval exercises and strategic exchanges, as well as on issues like climate change (Sharma, 2022). Trade between the two is also significant, totalling between 11 and 13 billion USD (Embassy of India, Paris, France, 2024, p. 4); this has been backed by numerous agreements and memoranda of understanding.

France has successfully expanded its relationship with India over the last decade. Shared statements such as the 2018 Joint Strategic Vision of India-France Cooperation in the Indian Ocean Region and the more expansive 2023 India-France Indo-Pacific Roadmap underscored that the "two countries believe in a free, open, inclusive, secure and peaceful Indo Pacific region" where "Our bilateral cooperation advances our mutual security and supports peace and stability in the Indo Pacific region" (Présidence de la République, 2023, p. 1). By invoking the Free and Open Indo-Pacific, a framework that has been advanced by the US and denounced by Chinese scholars as a containment measure, the target of the increasing Indo-French alignment is clear (Laskar, 2023). This rhetoric has been matched by concrete action, primarily in terms of shared defence exercises. Shared naval exercises between the two countries date back to the 1980s with the Varuna exercises, but they have been expanded, with the 2024 exercises including the first-ever European deployments of India's P8I aircraft, showing India's commitment to the relationship (The Hindu, 2024). Varuna and other new exercises such as La Pérouse allow France to visibly demonstrate its place in the Indo-Pacific, as well as its military might (The Economic Times, 2024).

The basis for the Indo-French partnership lies in their shared security interests in the region, which have become closer over the last decade. Like France, India has concerns about China's growing power as the two countries have various border disputes, which in 2020 resulted in a skirmish that killed 20 Indian soldiers. These security concerns play into India's actions (US Institute of Peace, 2020, p. 36). China is a clear check on India's own growing strength in the Indo-Pacific and constrains India's ability to build its own sphere of influence (Brewster, 2010, p. 5). Furthermore, both India and France wish to pursue an Indo-Pacific vision that is not overly dominated by US power, as both argue for positions of 'strategic autonomy' rather than total commitment to alliance blocs (de Estrada, 2023, p. 385). Some Indian scholars have thus gone as far as to conclude that "France and India are the best partners for each other in the Indian Ocean and the Indo-Pacific" (Seth, 2020, p. 230). The aforementioned expansion of relations between the two countries clearly demonstrates that the theoretical basis for their partnership has been realised.

Despite this successful expansion and the enthusiasm of Indian scholars for the partnership, there are clear challenges for closer alignment. For one, India's continued commitment to non-alignment precludes any possibility of an alliance or close military cooperation between the two. This is potentially an issue for France, which, as a founding member of NATO, has a very different approach, one that some contend "poses a substantial challenge to aligning their goals effectively, particularly in the face of China's growing assertiveness" (Gill, 2024). As there is limited possibility of further deepening the France-India connection, France can only expect to work with concrete deals in mind. In other aspects, their strategic alignment in the region is limited. While France aims to maintain its status quo in the region, India has bolder ambitions to expand its power and achieve nationalistic goals, potentially at the cost of overall regional stability, as evidenced by tensions with its neighbours (O'Donnell, 2024, p. 2). Although maintaining the rules-based order is crucial to France's maritime position, India has only weakly opposed China's actions in the South China Sea, as can be seen in its refusal to join in US freedom-of-navigation patrols (Singh, 2023). This may be due to India's own maritime dispute with Bangladesh, which in turn suggests India's lack of true commitment to the rules-based order (de Estrada, 2023, p. 394). Similarly, India's slide towards autocracy poses problems for India-France alignment as supporting democratic values forms some element of French foreign policy (de Estrada, 2023, p. 398). Thus, while France has developed this partnership of convenience effectively over the last decade, there remain reasonable doubts about how much further it can achieve French goals in the Indo-Pacific.

AUSTRALIA

Relations with Australia have not charted a smooth course over the last decade and are revealing of the flaws in France's Indo-Pacific strategy. France appeared to be successfully building up its relationship with Australia when, in 2018, President Macron declared that he hoped for the creation of a strategic axis between France, India and Australia, claiming, "We're not naive: if we want to be seen and respected by China as an equal partner, we must organise ourselves" (Reuters, 2018). This statement was built on the first-ever visit to Australia by a French President by Sarkozy in 2009, which had been followed up by a 2014 visit by President Hollande (Bremner, 2009). There were promising signs that France could manifest the same sort of constructive relationship it had achieved with India. The most significant cog in this strategy was the 2016 deal for French naval contractor DCNS (now Naval Group) to build twelve Attack-class submarines for Australia at a projected 50 billion AUD cost (Karp, 2016). France made a major effort to secure this deal, involving Defence Minister Jean-Yves Le Drian and Australian submarine insider Sean Costello to outmanoeuvre a rival Japanese proposal (Kelly et al., 2016). By securing such a key defence contract, France hoped to secure its collaboration with Australia and solidify a working relationship in the Indo-Pacific.

France's hopes did not pan out. The announcement of AUKUS in 2021, where Australia secured a new deal with the US and UK for eight nuclear-powered submarines, rendering the French contract surplus to requirements (Staunton and Day, 2023, pp. 11-18). The resulting diplomatic spat between France and Australia was vitriolic, and the significance of this breakdown in the two countries' relationship is undeniable, though there have been some steps to rehabilitate it since then. When Anthony Albanese came to power in Australia in 2022, he visited France shortly after gaining office and in a joint statement, the two countries affirmed their hopes for "building a closer and stronger bilateral relationship based on mutual trust and respect" (Prime Minister of Australia, 2022). The Australian government agreed to pay \$835 million AUD in compensation to Naval Group to help smooth over the dispute (Doran, 2022), yet French-Australian relations have not returned to pre-AUKUS levels of cooperation.

The collapse of the submarine deal was deeply revealing of the disconnect between France and Australia in two interlinked ways. Firstly, as Staunton and Day argue, "the Morrison government viewed the acquisition of nuclear-powered submarines through a transactional lens. The French, it was clear, did not: the deal with Australia was instead seen as an opportunity to build 'a strategic partnership'" (Staunton and Day, 2023, p. 12). Ultimately, France overestimated the importance of its deal with Australia. Secondly, and more significantly, AUKUS was symptomatic of Australia's wider security objectives, which are very different to France's. As Hugh White contends, "AUKUS... is about strengthening Australia's bond with America" and protecting Australia by tying it to a superpower in fear of possible war in the future (White, 2024, p. 24). This is clearly in direct contradiction with France's own attempt to plot a third way in the Indo-Pacific, rather than total alignment with the US (Fathi, 2021). The failure of France to align Australia with its vision of a peaceful third way is thus proof of the flawed nature of France's bilateral strategy in the Indo-Pacific.

JAPAN & OTHER PARTNERSHIPS

Another important element of France's strategy in the Indo-Pacific is the establishment of closer relationships with Japan. Trade between the two countries is significant, as Japan is France's second-biggest trade partner in Asia, and much of the relations between the two have been limited to trade-related concerns (Mellet, 2022, p. 250). Defence and strategic collaboration is more limited, but has still grown in recent years since the 2013 elevation of relations to an 'exceptional partnership (partenariat d'exception)' (Pajon, 2018, p. 11). In a 2019 roadmap, the two countries confirmed their joint commitment to "conduct concrete co-operations within the framework of a partnership for the Indo-Pacific in order to make this region a space of peace and prosperity" (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan, 2019, p. 1), while the countries' foreign and defence ministers meet yearly. Japan has many of the same interests as France, such as democratic values and opposition to China's incursions on maritime law and is thus supportive of France's freedom-of-navigation patrols in the South China Sea (Reuters, 2017). Céline Pajon argues that thanks to France's position on the UNSC and nuclear armament, "France stands out as a partner of choice for a Japan that is keen to normalise its defence posture" (Pajon, 2018, p. 11).

Still, there are limits to the potential of France-Japan relations. Much like Australia, Japan is closely aligned with the US, forming part of the Quad and working extensively with the US military. While this has committed Japan to clear opposition to China, France's aim of a third way prevents it from taking such a hard-line approach. While this limits how closely France can align itself with Japan, Japan likewise struggles to understand how France claims to be geopolitically neutral in the Indo-Pacific while elsewhere being a member of NATO (Delamotte, 2024). France-Japan cooperation, while successfully expanded in the 2010s, has not progressed much further in other areas, such as cybersecurity, and it is doubtful whether France and Japan will be able to close the gap in the future (Pajon, 2018, pp. 13-4).

France's bilateral actions in the Indo-Pacific are not limited to the key middle powers of India, Australia, and Japan, but extend to numerous other countries. France has begun working more closely with Indonesia through bilateral dialogues and burgeoning defence ties (Ministère de l'Europe et des Affaires étrangères, 2024). Indonesian purchases of 42 French Rafale jets and two Scorpène-class submarines (Idrus, 2024) are a first step to bringing the two states together. Collaboration with other ASEAN nations, such as Vietnam, has also expanded, with France declaring in 2018 that Vietnam is "a key partner for our interests in Southeast Asia and in the Indo-Pacific region" (Philippe, 2018). Their relationship has been framed in terms of defence by three Defence Strategy Dialogues held since 2016 (Hoai, 2023). France's third way is an appealing prospect for ASEAN nations that equally want to avoid being caught between the US-China conflict. As Tran Thi Mong Tuyen argues, "France's non-participation in alliances like the Quad and AUKUS means ASEAN doesn't need to worry about being pressured to take sides", and thus bilateral relations in this region offer good prospects for France (Tuyen, 2024). Despite this, France's actions with smaller Indo-Pacific nations have been far more limited than with middle powers, and its geographical distance means that until France invests more heavily, this opportunity to build its third way will remain unfulfilled (Tuyen, 2024).

ASSESSING FRANCE'S BILATERAL ACHIEVEMENTS

It is clear that France has successfully expanded its bilateral commitments in the Indo-Pacific. With India, Japan and other Indo-Pacific countries, France has demonstrably achieved successes in building its connections and legitimacy in the region, although its attempt to do the same with Australia has followed a considerably rockier path. While the individual evaluations of France's bilateral relations are revealing of its varied approaches to alliance building, assessing the overall achievements of these actions reveals further insights as to the limits of France's strategy.

One clear success can be identified in the growing perception of the French presence in the Indo-Pacific as legitimate. Simply by negotiating the numerous agreements it has in the region, France proves its own legitimacy, a fact evident in the joint statements that take pains to describe France as a "strategically located resident power" (Présidence de la République, 2023, p. 1). This legitimacy extends beyond rhetoric into real achievements for France too, as can be seen in the international response to the ongoing political crisis in New Caledonia. France's attempts to prevent New Caledonian independence, including a controversial 2021 referendum that was widely boycotted by the indigenous Kanak population, have been widely described in media outlets as colonial in nature (Reeves, 2024). France's development of bilateral ties in the region, however, has protected it from any substantial international criticism, including from countries such as Australia that claim to support indigenous reconciliation movements (Fisher, 2024). This is a concrete achievement of recent French foreign policy, as previously in the 1980s, Australia had pushed for greater New Caledonian agency and UN acknowledgement of the islands as a non-self-governing territory, against French wishes (George, 2024). India, Japan, and others have also remained non-committal on the situation (Kyodo News, 2024). The pursuit of greater legitimacy through bilateral relations has thus helped France to protect its own sovereignty and security. Despite this, France still suffers from limited involvement in regional multilateral organisations, suggesting that regional legitimacy has not been fully gained.

With regard to carving out a third way in the Indo-Pacific, France's achievements are more mixed. As much as France has been able to support the development of its own relations with Indo-Pacific middle powers, this has not been converted into tangible foreign policy changes. The failures in France's approach to Australia have already been discussed, but France has more widely failed to shift the attitudes of its potential allies, while new regional developments like AUKUS only weaken hopes of a French-led alternative. Australia, India, and Japan all remain part of the Quad, an American-built

group that is expanding its actions further and is the antithesis to France's third way (Hunnicut and Brunnstrom, 2024). Tensions in the Indo-Pacific have continued to intensify over the last decade, further evidence that the third way is yet to materialise. The third way is a highly ambitious project for France to embark on, and it is doubtful that France has the weight to effectively shift the position of other Indo-Pacific states. Therefore, it may be the case that, as Pugliese suggests, the third way will "become more and more discreet" (Pugliese, 2023, p. 83).

The entire French project in the Indo-Pacific falls prey to French exceptionalism, France's belief that it remains a great power with high status in global politics, constituting a long-standing fissure that still "forms the basis of French foreign policy today" (Rieker, 2017, p. 33). France's hopes of creating a third way in the Indo-Pacific are revealing of its overestimation of its own importance in the region. Staunton and Day argue that this disconnect contributed to the collapse of the France-Australia submarine deal due to Australian "misjudgement of the extent to which French exceptionalism continues to pervade its foreign policy" (Staunton and Day, 2023, p. 18). The dissonance between France and its potential allies is most pronounced in the Indo-Pacific due to France's lingering colonial presence and limited capacity to involve itself in the region. As much as France may invest in the Indo-Pacific, by virtue of geography, its focus will always remain in Europe, and Indo-Pacific states will remain cognizant of that fact. Since the 2022 invasion of Ukraine, France's attention has been further shifted away from the Indo-Pacific as it attempts to assert itself as a leader in the EU through strong commitments to Ukraine (Zamiatin and Yurchyshyn, 2024, p. 2).

For all its setbacks, France has still successfully pivoted to the region and has reinforced its position and legitimacy as an Indo-Pacific state. France's project of building up individual relations in the region, when assessed as a whole, shows it to be a valuable strategy. Overall, Indo-Pacific middle powers have welcomed French cooperation, showing the validity of France's approach. However, the issues with France's stance in the region, such as its inability to chart a third way and realign potential allies to its vision, are unlikely to dissipate, and there are signs that its position will only become more difficult to navigate with time. Tensions in New Caledonia and other French possessions like Mayotte will continue to bubble, and continued US-China hostility poses long-standing problems for France. Recent developments like AUKUS further demonstrate the continued difficulties France suffers from in maintaining its position in a peaceful Indo-Pacific, which its bilateral tactics have been unable to solve.

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